

An industrial demonstrator

FAIRness at OAS

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FAIRness of the OAS demonstrator

- OAS is a company specialized in
 - Weighing systems
 - Plant construction
 - Process control technologies
 - **Yard Management**
- The demonstrator within OntoCommons aims at improving effectiveness and responsiveness of decision-making in logistics control systems based on data sharing built around big volume data streams semantically described by dedicated PSS ontologies
- Data analysed: Yard Management – Site Definition - Site.xml

Yard Management

Example of a Site Definition

```

1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
2 <Site xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema">
3   <Name>ReferenceSite</Name>
4   <Version>1</Version>
5   <CurrentSiteEnvironment>DefaultEnvironment</CurrentSiteEnvironment>
6   <Modified>2020-05-22T12:34:56.7899999Z</Modified>
7   <ModifiedBy>PyLod</ModifiedBy>
8   <Location>Reference Site Location</Location>
9   <Description>Reference Site - can be used to create developer-specific sites for local testing</Description>
10  <Objects>
11    <Object>
12      <Bmk>WB02</Bmk>
13      <Name>Waage Ausfahrt</Name>
14      <TypeId>SCALES</TypeId>
15      <Description>Ausgangswaage</Description>
16      <Version>1.0.0</Version>
17    </Object>
18    <Object>
19      <Bmk>WB04</Bmk>
20      <Name>Waage Einfahrt</Name>
21      <TypeId>SCALES</TypeId>
22      <Description>Eingangswaage</Description>
23      <Version>1.0.0</Version>
24    </Object>
25    <Object>
26      <Bmk>PA001</Bmk>
27      <Name>Parkbereich Check-In</Name>
28      <TypeId>PARKAREA</TypeId>
29      <Description>Parkbereich Check-In</Description>
30      <Version>1.0.0</Version>
31    </Object>
32  </Objects>
33  <ObjectLinks>
34    <ObjectLink>
35      <Name>WaagenLink</Name>
36      <From>WB02</From>
37      <To>WB04</To>
38      <Type>Correlated</Type>

```


Assessability (some answers)

- Fully implemented:
 - Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data and can be accessed manually
 - Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record & Data identifier resolves to a digital object
 - Metadata and Data are accessed through a standardised (free access) protocol & can be accessed automatically
- Being implemented:
 - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed

Findability (some answers)

Findability

OAS

- — Fully implemented:
 - — Metadata and Data are fully identified by a persistent identifier
 - — Metadata and Data are identified by a globally unique identifier
 - — Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery

- — Being implemented:
 - — Metadata to be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed

Interoperability (some answers)

- — Fully implemented:
 - — Metadata and Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format
 - — Metadata and Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

- — Being implemented:
 - — Data includes references to other data

- — Under consideration / planning
 - — Metadata and Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

Reusability (some answers)

- In the planning phase
 - Metadata and Data complies with a community standard
 - Metadata and Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard (e.g. an ontology)

Reusability

OAS

FAIRness of the OAS demonstrator - Challenges

- The OAS use case in terms of “FAIRness”:
 - In accessibility and findability dimension, most applicable principles already in a fully implemented stage
 - OAS uses the Yard Definition in current SW development and in their products
 - There is room for improvement regarding Interoperability and especially Reusability dimensions
 - Yard Definition is only used internally up to now and grew over time without a defined plan with respect to interoperability & reusability
- Challenges
 - How to improve Interoperability of data outside of OAS Ecosystem
 - How to improve Reusability of data outside of OAS Ecosystem

FAIRness of the OAS demonstrator

- Opportunities

- Use OntoCommons best practices to achieve a higher FAIRness level
 - Using OntoCommons LOT methodology and OntoCommons tools to build domain ontologies that will form the metadata basis of the Yard Management ecosystem data
 - Using ontologies to facilitate both
 - interoperability (by using qualified references to other metadata) and
 - reusability (by expressing metadata and data with community standards)

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